

Review Article

Method Development and Validation for the Simultaneous Estimation of Cefepime and Enmetazobactam in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage form by RP-HPLC Method

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ABSTRACT

A rapid, sensitive, and high precise reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed for the simultaneous quantification of Cefepime and Enmetazobactam using a Waters HPLC system. Chromatographic separation was achieved on a Inertsil ODS C18 column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm particle size) maintained at ambient temperature. The mobile phase consisted of acetonitrile and buffer in the ratio of 80 :20(v/v), which was filtered through a 0.45μm membrane filter prior to use. The flow rate was maintained at 1.0 mL/min, and detection was carried out at 228 nm using PDA detector.

INTRODUCTION

Exblifep is a combination antibiotic used for complicated urinary tract infections (cUTIs) that contains two antibiotics, cefepime and enmetazobactam. Exblifep is used when the bacteria causing the UTI is resistant to other antibiotics, especially if the resistance is due to Extended Spectrum Beta Lactamases (ESBLs).

Exblifep contains cefepime (Maxipime), which is fourth-generation cephalosporin combined with enmetazobactam, which is a beta-lactamase

inhibitor. Exblifep is given as an IV infusion that takes about 2 hours and is given every 8 hours for 7 to 14 days.

Exblifep received FDA approval to treat adults (18 years and older) with complicated UTI, including kidney infection (pyelonephritis) caused by specific bacteria Escherichia coli, Klebsiella pneumoniae, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Proteus mirabilis, and Enterobacter cloacae complex, that susceptible to Exblifep.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

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Preparation of Stock solution: Accurately weigh 125 mg of Enmetazobactam and 120 mg of Cefepime separately in a 100ml volumetric flask sonicated for 20 minutes. Take 10ml of each of each solution and place them in a 100ml volumetric flask. Next, add mobile phase, and after 10 minutes, sonicate the mixture.

Preparation of working standard solution: 10mg of the drugs Cefepime and Enmetazobactam were weighed, and 10 ml of mobile phase was added to each of two separate 10 ml volumetric flasks. The mixture was then sonicated for 20 minutes to obtain 1000 ppm, then taking 1ml of each solution and diluting it to 10ml with mobile phase.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Method validation: Validation parameters include specificity, linearity, range, accuracy, precision, limit of detection, limit of quantification, robustness and assay (1-6).

Specificity: Specificity is the ability to assessing equivocally the analyte in the presence of components which may be expected to be present. Typically, these components include impurities, degradants, matrix etc. Blank solution and standard solutions of Cefepime (40µg/ml) and Enmetazobactam. (40µg/ ml) were injected into the HPLC system. The peak purity data of Cefepime and Enmetazobactam. were compared. There should not be any interference at the retention time of the main peaks.

Linearity: Linearity for the drugs Cefepime and Enmetazobactam (17-27) was determined by preparing the standard solutions at six concentrations levels in six replicates in the range of 20-70µg/ml Cefepime and 20-70µg/ml for and Enmetazobactam hydrochloride from stock solution. The linearity charts of Cefepime and

Enmetazo bactam was shown in the figure no 2&3. The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.9996 and 0.9994 for Cefepime and Enmetazo bactam respectively. Linearity results were tabulated in table 2.

Accuracy: Accuracy was performed by spiking known amounts of standard solution to sample solution at three different concentrations levels (50%, 100%, 150%) and there by analyzed for %RSD which should not be more than 2.0. The % recovery was calculated and the results was reported in table no. 3 & 4.

Precision: The precision (7-12) of the analytical method was studied by injecting six replicates of standard containing 40µg/ml of Cefepime and 40µg/ml of Enmetazo bactam which were injected into HPLC system. The % RSD was calculated and the results were reported in the table no.5 & 6.

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ): The limit of detection was defined as the concentration which yields a signal - to - noise ratio 3:1 whereas the limit of quantification was calculated to be the lowest concentration that could be measured with signal - to - noise ratio 10:1. LOD and LOQ were calculated from slope and standard deviation. The results were tabulated in table no. 7.

Robustness: The smallest deliberate changes in method like change in flow rate are made but there were no predictable changes in the results and are in the range as per ICH guidelines. Conditions like decrease in flow rate (0.8 ml/min), increase in flow rate (1.2 ml/min) was maintained and samples were injected in duplicate manner. System suitability parameters were not much affected and all the parameters were passed. % RSD was found to be within the limits and results were tabulated in table no. 8.

Assay: Assay was conducted on marketed formulation and mean % assay was found. The results were tabulated in table no. 9.

Table1: Optimised Chromatographic Conditions

Parameter	Method
Stationary Phase (column)	Inertsil -ODS C18 (250 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ)
Mobile Phase	Methanol and Acetonitrile(80:20)
Flow rate (ml/min)	1.0 ml/min
Run time (minutes)	14 min
Temperature in the column (°C)	Ambient
Injection volume (μl)	20
Detection wavelength (nm)	262nm
Drug RT (min)	6.120 min for Cefepime and 9.336 for Enmetazobactam.

Figure 1: Optimised Chromatogram

Table 2: Linearity data of Cefepime and Enmetazobactam

Cefepime		Enmetazobactam	
Conc (μg/ml)	Peak area	Conc (μg/ml)	Peak area
20	442574	20	1867314
30	663321	30	2726631
40	863425	40	3613860
50	1086345	50	4385621
60	1296547	60	5263754
70	1535742	70	6132485

Figure 2: Calibration curve of Cefepime

Figure 3: Calibration curve of Enmetazobactam

Table 3: Accuracy Data of Cefepime

Concentration % of spiked level	Amount added (ppm)	Amount found (ppm)	% Recovery	Statistical Analysis of % Recovery	
50% - 1	20	20.12	100.14	MEAN	99.93
50% - 2	20	19.98	99.91		
50% - 3	20	19.94	99.89	%RSD	0.74
100 % - 1	40	40.14	100.12	MEAN	99.84
100 % - 2	40	39.96	99.98		
100% - 3	40	39.86	99.75	%RSD	0.639
150% - 1	60	59.94	99.99	MEAN	100.04
150% - 2	60	60.01	100.02		
150% - 3	60	60.02	100.02	%RSD	0.667

Table 4: Accuracy Data for Enmetazobactam

Concentration % of spiked level	Amount added (ppm)	Amount found (ppm)	% Recovery	Statistical Analysis of % Recovery	
50% - 1	20	19.93	99.97	MEAN	99.98
50% - 2	20	19.84	99.87		
50% - 3	20	20.05	100.4	%RSD	0.867
100 % - 1	40	39.90	99.84	MEAN	99.96
100 % - 2	40	40.04	100.06		
100% - 3	40	40.01	100.04	%RSD	0.687
150% - 1	60	59.98	99.97	MEAN	99.94
150% - 2	60	59.95	99.93		
150% - 3	60	59.92	99.91	%RSD	0.687

Table 5: System Precision data of Cefepime and Enmetazobactam

Sr. No	Cefepime	Enmetazobactam
1	865021	3604637
2	865327	3607638
3	865674	3609784
4	865780	3612341
5	865732	3606721
Mean	865506.8	3608224
SD	324.6686	2951.79
% RSD	0.037512	0.081807

Table 6: Method Precision data of Cefepime and Enmetazobactam

Sr. No	Cefepime	Enmetazobactam
1	865237	3607684
2	865762	3604672
3	865760	3605241
4	865091	3606754
5	865374	3607878
6	865767	3606752
Mean	865498.5	3606497
SD	303.2641	1292.7
% RSD	0.035039	0.035844

Table 7: LOD and LOQ data of Cefepime and Enmetazobactam

Drug Name	LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
Cefepime	0.11	0.33
Enmetazobactam	0.09	0.27

Table 8: Robustness data of Cefepime and Enmetazobactam

Sr No	Drug Name	Condition	Peak area	% RSD
1	Cefepime	Decreased Flow rate of 0.8 ml/min	864680	0.037
2		Increased Flow rate of 1.2 ml/min	866350	0.0038
3	Enmetazobactam	Decreased Flow rate of 0.8 ml/min	359512	0.089
4		Increased Flow rate of 1.2 ml/min	362053	0.066

Table 9: Assay data Cefepime and Enmetazobactam

Sr. No	Peak area of Cefepime	% Assay	Peak area of Enmetazobactam	% Assay
1	865354	99.24	3608756	101.57
2	865037		3605937	
3	865762		3602734	
4	865972		3607961	

CONCLUSION

The developed RP-HPLC method was validated as per ICH guidelines. All the system suitability parameters were within the range as stated by ICH guidelines. Interference peaks were not observed in blank, standard and sample chromatogram. Hence simple, precise and accurate, sensitive, specific and robust method was developed and validated. This can be used in quality control department with respect to routine analysis.

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